

**Scoping considerations
for the request addressed to the
European Group on Ethics in Science and New Technologies (EGE)
to develop Opinions on
Planetary Ethics — Ethics and the Green Transition**

The questions raised by what has been referred to as the triple planetary crisis¹ (climate change, biodiversity loss and pollution) and its policy response are deeply ethical. They concern the relationship between humans and the environment, our responsibility vis-à-vis nature on which life on Earth depends, and human action, ongoing and future, in the face of one of the greatest challenges that humanity has faced – qualified by the European Council as an “existential threat to humanity”².

The European Commission plays a key role in governing the European and global transition to sustainable ways of living. It has been and will be pursuing manifold actions towards this, notably under the European Green Deal.³ In this context, the European Commission seeks advice from the European Group on Ethics in Science and New Technologies (EGE) in the areas listed below.

These areas represent three different ways to ask about *our relationship with, and our responsibilities towards, nature – and towards ‘each other’, now and in the future.*

(1) THE GREEN TRANSITION AS A JUST TRANSITION

Climate change and environmental degradation (including rising global temperatures; droughts and floodings; air, water, marine and soil pollution; biodiversity loss and deterioration of ecosystems; over-exploitation of natural resources) are affecting all individuals, communities and regions globally, in particular the less affluent ones that have contributed little to climate change and environmental degradation. Particular attention needs to be paid to ensuring inclusivity, fairness and equity in the transition to sustainable ways of living.

This involves carefully assessing impacts of climate change, biodiversity loss and pollution and of policies developed to address these, on different social groups. A non-inclusive and socially unjust transition, or one that is perceived as such, can lead to societal rejection of measures, with detrimental environmental and social consequences. Ensuring synergies between the green transition and reducing inequalities appears essential in the move towards climate neutrality and resilience. In this, the people, democracy, civic action and inclusive societal deliberation play a central role.

Another critical aspect for climate policy is the inter-generational dimension, with future generations exposed to worsening conditions due to the interdependent environmental crises.

Beyond human-centric concerns, there are also calls for eco-centric perspectives about the value and the rights of other species and of ecosystems (inter-species justice, see also the section on “The value of nature and valuing nature”).

¹ [What is the Triple Planetary Crisis? | UNFCCC](#)

² [Council conclusions on Climate and Energy Diplomacy - Delivering on the external dimension of the European Green Deal, adopted at the 3784th meeting of the Council on 25 January 2021](#)

³ [The European Green Deal | European Commission](#)

EU policy background

The EU has acknowledged the need for measures that ensure fairness and equity in the context of its Green Deal objectives, which is also at the core of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development and the Sustainable Development Goals.

For instance, EU climate policy already contained at its core fairness aspects, but directed at Member State level. Member States with high GDP per capita income levels were attributed more stringent greenhouse gas reduction targets, and lower income Member States received a larger share of the auctioning revenues from the EU emission trading system. This toolbox was further strengthened under the Green Deal with two new EU funds that complement specifically its broader socio-economic efforts.

The EU's [Just Transition Mechanism](#) addresses the social and economic effects of the transition through three pillars. The *Just Transition Fund* of €19.2 billion is expected to mobilise around EUR €25.4 billion in investments in regions that will face the greatest transition challenges. The *InvestEU Just Transition Scheme* will provide a budgetary guarantee under the InvestEU programme across the four policy windows and an InvestEU Advisory Hub that will act as a central entry point for advisory support requests. It is expected to mobilise €10-15 billion in mostly private sector investments. A new *Public Sector Loan Facility* will combine €1.5 billion of grants financed from the EU budget with €10 billion of loans from the European Investment Bank, to mobilise €18.5 billion of public investment.

The [Social Climate Fund](#) has been established to address the social impacts arising from the new emissions trading system for buildings and road transport (ETS2) on the most vulnerable households, transport users, and micro-enterprises, in particular citizens in energy or transport poverty. It will mobilise at least EUR 86.7 billion between 2026 and 2032 and will provide funding to Member States to support measures and investments in increased energy efficiency and renovation of buildings, decarbonisation of heating and cooling of buildings, including the integration of energy from renewable sources, and granting improved access to zero- and low-emission mobility and transport. These measures and investments need to principally benefit vulnerable households, micro-enterprises, or transport users. Moreover, Member States will have the option of spending up to 37.5% of the resources on temporary direct income support.

[Article 37 of the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union](#) provides that a high level of environmental protection must be integrated in EU policies, but does not recognise an individual [right to a healthy environment](#).

The [Council Recommendation on ensuring a fair transition towards climate neutrality](#) of June 2022 is an integral part of the 'Fit for 55' package and in line with the objective of the [European Green Deal](#). Through this Recommendation, Member States committed to put in place comprehensive policy packages focusing on employment, skills and social policies that address the country-, sector- and region-specific challenges and needs. It also provides concrete guidance on how to devise and implement measures to address the impacts of the transition on workers and households, based on a robust evidence-base and a whole-of-society approach, involving social partners and stakeholders in all stages of policymaking and at all levels.

Furthermore, the [Council Recommendation on strengthening social dialogue](#) of June 2023 provides concrete guidance to Member States on how to best devise and implement measures supporting social dialogue and collective bargaining to address the employment and social impacts of the green transition. Well-functioning collective bargaining is also an important means to ensure decent wages, essential in the just transition process. In this regard, democracy at work is an important aspect which encompasses any form of cooperation between the workers and the employers, and on which the [Council adopted conclusions at its meeting of 27-28 November 2023](#).

This Opinion should be completed by the end of Q1 2025.

Questions to the EGE:

What are important ethical considerations for the development of policies in support of a just transition, considering the potential dilemmas and trade-offs linked to the green transition in relation to environmental goals and to immediate social imperatives?

In this context, the Commission is currently working on the following questions: What are good ways to avoid or to mitigate negative impacts of the green transition as regards social justice and labour aspects? How to foster co-benefits between climate mitigation and adaptation, environmental action, and wellbeing, in particular for vulnerable groups? How can the right to a healthy environment be further strengthened in EU policymaking? How can green collective bargaining and the involvement of social partners in all stages of policymaking, and at all levels – including in company decision making processes in relation to the just transition – be strengthened, and are there any specific related ethical issues? How can an inclusive and democratic transition be ensured that also involves civil society, and citizens at large, in line with a true whole-of-society approach?

To what do governance institutions need to pay attention when designing, communicating, implementing and monitoring their transition policies in order for real change in businesses, economies and societies to happen? What makes policies socially acceptable and supported by individuals' choices (also in the face of climate change fatigue, as well as climate change denial and disinformation)? How can communication be improved on potential distributional effects and (future) costs of delays in policy implementation, policy reversals or inaction?

What are important aspects to be considered by the EU as regards a just transition on the global level? In a global society (and economy), where the population is growing and inequalities are increasing, what are the incentives for the wealthier countries or groups of population to move towards more sustainable, responsible, frugal lifestyles, to distribute wealth and use of natural resources equitably?

What are important ethical considerations as regards the responsibility for, and rights of, future generations? How to determine the freedom of choice of current vs future generations?

(2) THE VALUE OF NATURE AND VALUING NATURE

It is necessary to go beyond monetisation approaches, while noting that among the manifold reactions to the biodiversity and climate crises are attempts to value nature in economic and monetary terms. The Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES), for example, highlights that most policymaking approaches have prioritised a narrow set of values at the expense of both nature and society, supporting short-term profit and 'economic growth'. It found that achieving sustainable and just futures requires institutions that enable a recognition and integration of broader understandings of the intrinsic value of nature and its value for human and other forms of life.⁴

Questions about the value of nature can be assessed from a variety of viewpoints and deeply relate to questions about the place of humans in nature, as part of nature, and vis-à-vis other parts of nature, as well as to questions about the sustainability of our current economic system ('green growth', 'degrowth', 'beyond growth', "post-growth").

Relevant conceptual and analytical lenses in this area of discussion may also include anthropocentrism, speciesism, ecocentrism (incl. perspectives from 'indigenous' communities); global justice; stewardship,

⁴ [Assessment Report on Diverse Values and Valuation of Nature | UNEP - UN Environment Programme](#)

custodianship, ownership; intergenerational and interspecies ethics; relational ethics, care ethics; the role of science, innovation and new technologies.

EU policy background:

As part of the European Green Deal, the [Biodiversity Strategy for 2030](#) is the EU's plan to put biodiversity on the path to recovery by 2030. It contains specific commitments and actions to protect nature and reverse the degradation of ecosystems, building on existing European nature laws.

The Birds and Habitats Directives (“[Nature Directives](#)”) are the EU's oldest environmental laws. They form the backbone of EU biodiversity policy and are the legal basis for Natura 2000 – the largest coordinated network of protected areas in the world.

The [Environmental Liability Directive](#) has been providing an EU-wide liability regime for environmental damage. By making those that have caused environmental damage liable for remediation, it provides a strong incentive to avoid damage occurring in the first place. It also makes those whose activities threaten the environment liable for taking preventive action.

In the context of the [Better Regulation agenda](#) (with its [Better Regulation Toolbox](#)), the European Commission aims to ensure that all legislative proposals contribute to the 2030 sustainable development agenda. It requires that impacts in qualitative, quantitative and monetary terms are assessed where possible.

The European Green Deal, in addition to previous specifications, centrally builds on sustainable economic growth. As described above, funds that would trigger ‘green’ growth are core parts of the EU's current environmental and climate policies (as also explained the European Commission's [answer](#) to the [Parliamentary Question E-002894/2023](#). Some of its instruments are based on approaches that attempt to monetarily capture the value of nature, notably the [Emissions Trading System](#), while the [Carbon Removal Certification Framework](#) aims at creating transparency, and the [Regulation on land, land use change and forestry](#) establishes targets on carbon removal.

This Opinion should be completed by the end of Q3 2025.

Questions to the EGE:

Which assumptions about the value of nature, biodiversity, ecosystems and of the relationship of humans to nature should underpin policy decisions? How are these dimensions integrated into (economic) policymaking at EU and national levels, and in underlying models used for impact assessment, policy design, monitoring and evaluation? On this basis, what kinds of governance action are required, also with regard to the further development of the European Green Deal and of what is to follow it, and the EU's strategies and actions in the global context?

What are important ethical considerations as regards conceptualisations about the rights and standing of non-human parts of nature? Who is best placed to invoke, enshrine, and adjudicate these rights – and on what basis?

How are approaches that value nature, and human actions with effect on nature, in economic terms to be assessed from an ethical perspective?

What are important ethical perspectives as regards socio-economic systems and the need for a global transition to sustainability?

(3) SOLAR RADIATION MODIFICATION

In the context of accelerated global warming, the option of deliberate large-scale intervention in the Earth's natural systems (often referred to as “geoengineering” or “climate intervention”), such as solar radiation modification (SRM), is attracting more attention. SRM refers to proposals to increase the reflection of shortwave radiation (sunlight) back to space to counteract anthropogenic warming and some of its harmful impacts, for example via stratospheric aerosol interventions, marine cloud brightening or ground-based albedo modifications.

Such intentional large-scale atmospheric interventions involve multiple known and unknown hazards on several levels and raise ethical questions, which the European Commission wants to understand and address. SRM deployment would require international governance, with particular attention paid to ethical questions and risk assessment and management. There are many risks connected to SRM and, even if technically feasible and proven safe, SRM would provide only temporary alleviation of some of the impacts and not a solution to global warming. Nevertheless, it can be expected that interest in some forms of SRM is likely to grow in the future, in particular in case of temperature overshoot due to insufficient mitigation and the risk of climate tipping points being reached.

An assessment of risks related to moral hazards; global and inter-generational justice; and geopolitical risks in the context of accelerating global warming is needed.

EU policy background

The European Commission does not consider SRM to be a solution to climate change, as it does not address the root cause of the problem: the increase of global greenhouse gas (GHG) concentrations in the atmosphere. The only way to halt global warming and lessen the impacts of climate change is by bringing GHG emissions to net-zero and below. The EU therefore works towards its objective of achieving climate neutrality and resilience by 2050 ([European Climate Law](#)), reducing GHG emissions by 55% by 2030 ([Fit for 55](#)), and adapting to climate change ([Adaptation Strategy](#)) by focusing on a wide range of measures.

For the European Commission, a deliberate large-scale intervention in the Earth system via, for example, SRM deployment, in the current state of technological development, represents an unacceptable level of risk for humans and the environment. There is no clear scientific knowledge on the impact and consequences such actions would entail, and no comprehensive governance rules are developed at this stage. The Convention on Biological Diversity, the London Convention and London Protocol, and the Montreal Protocol, for example, impose restrictions on geoengineering.

Guided by the precautionary principle, the European Commission and the High Representative of the Union for Foreign Affairs and Security Policy support international efforts to comprehensively assess the risks and uncertainties of large-scale climate interventions, including of SRM, and promote discussions on a potential international framework for its governance, including on research-related aspects.

The European Commission also launched a coordination and support action under Horizon Europe ([Horizon-CL5-2023-D1-01-08](#)) to explore conditions that could lead to the development of a possible governance framework for experimental research in the area of SRM.

The European Commission has also asked the Group of Chief Scientific Advisors to provide, by autumn 2024, recommendations to inform the Commission's position on SRM focusing on risks and opportunities associated with research on it and with its potential deployment, as well as on options for a governance system for research and potential deployment.

This Opinion should be completed by the end of Q3 2024.

Questions to the EGE:

What are the most important ethical considerations in relation to solar radiation modification techniques? On the basis of what is currently known or can currently be assumed about this set of technologies, under which circumstances, if any, could their development and deployment be considered ethical?

What are the relevant ethical perspectives as regards the international governance of solar radiation modification?

HORIZONTAL, CROSS-CUTTING AND OTHER IMPORTANT ASPECTS

Bringing together the three above sections or facets are considerations of justice and of governance, as well as key underpinning questions:

How does this challenge the theories and practices of ethics itself?

How does this challenge or complicate the notion that climate change (or biodiversity loss, or pollution, etc.) is ‘the overarching issue’?

How does this challenge or complicate the interplay between forms of transitions and forms (understandings, practices) of democracy, inclusion and cohesion?

Against that backdrop, it will be of major added value if the Opinions can consider not just important questions of a narrower nature but also the bigger picture, in an integrative, systems-wide approach (systems thinking, integrative thinking, complexity, ‘wicked problem’); if they can analyse framings themselves; if they can discuss questions around the ethics and governance framework for the transition (questioning existing systems and proposing alternative or additional ones); if they can identify further important issues (including such that may be overlooked because of their ethical dimension); if they can incorporate considerations about science and technology, research and innovation, also including the social sciences and the humanities, and also including questions of global priority setting and distribution.
